

Webinar Recommendation using NLP

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Abstract— Webinars are the cornerstone of knowledge broadcasting for the academic community, providing a crucial platform for researchers and academicians to remain on the advanced of their respective fields, while also nurturing collaborative learning. The traditional process of identifying and selecting relevant webinars can be difficult and time-consuming. To address this challenge, our proposed system offers a streamlined solution. Users are now required to provide their areas of interest, and the system takes charge of the rest, presenting them with tailored event recommendations. This system is supported by a comprehensive framework that leverages the capabilities of Natural Language Processing (NLP), specifically the TF-IDF and cosine similarity techniques. These NLP methods enable the system to realize the textual content of webinars and user preferences, resulting in a remarkably precise and relevant recommendation system. Moreover, our research explores into a comparative analysis with spaCy, a renowned NLP library. This comparative assessment illuminates the unique advantages and limitations of various NLP approaches within the context of webinar recommendation systems. Our system enhances how researchers and academicians engage with webinars. It saves time and offers precise event recommendations aligned with user interests, outperforming spaCy in accuracy and relevance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Personalized content recommendation systems are more important than ever in this modern digital era, where infinite knowledge is just a click away. These technologies can prove very beneficial to webinars, which are a great way to share information and experience. Exploring the domain of "Webinar Recommendation using Natural Language Processing (NLP)," here we illuminate the potential of NLP methods like as cosine similarity and TF-IDF.

We start our research with the basics of TF-IDF, a method that enables us to arrive at significant conclusions from text. To provide advanced content-based recommendations, we generate feature vectors that capture both user interests and webinar descriptions. The measure of choice for determining the relation between attendees and their webinars turns out to be the fundamental idea of cosine similarity.

This also includes a comparative analysis in a significant manner. We evaluate NLP-based recommendations and investigate their performance in comparison with a different method that makes use of the well-known NLP library spaCy.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Yin et. al. [1] introduces a novel two-stage framework for analyzing social event participation, focusing on both user and event organizer selections. It adapts the Gale-Shapley algorithm to create utility functions, estimating user profiling for event selection and event rules for attendee selection. The study demonstrates that this two-way selection approach improves the prediction of event invitations and acceptances compared to one-way selection methods, highlighting its potential to better understand the decision-making process in social event participation.

Cao et. al. [2] came up with a method that uses different kinds of information to figure out what events people might like. They made a special model to understand how everything is connected. Then, they looked at things like how events are related, when they happen, where they are, and what they are about. They used all this info to give events a score based on what people might like.

Snigdha et. al. [3] describes a movie recommendation system that uses TF-IDF vectorization to create feature vectors for movies based on their genres, keywords, cast, crew, and overview. Then, it uses cosine similarity to measure the similarity between movies and recommend the most similar ones to the user. The paper also presents a web-based user interface for the system and evaluates its performance using various metrics.

Kunde et. al. [4] presents a hybrid video recommendation system that uses content-based filtering and collaborative filtering techniques. It uses TF-IDF vectorization to create feature vectors for videos based on their titles, descriptions, tags, and categories. Then, it uses cosine similarity to find the most similar videos to the user's preferences. It also uses user ratings and feedback to improve the recommendations.

Muthurasu et. al. [5] presents a recommendation methodology that recommends courses to students based on the similarity between courses taken by the target student and other students. It aims to provide an effective course recommendation using multiple techniques such as TF-IDF vectorization, cosine similarity, k-means clustering, and association rule mining. It also evaluates the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed methodology.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

As users register on the website, information about their interests is gathered along with details of webinars registered, making sure that data privacy laws are followed and that the quality of the data is maintained for recommendation reasons.

B. Data Pre-processing

Data preparation starts with tokenizing content, encoding webinar descriptions, and cleaning user-entered interests. Before using the data for webinar suggestions, quality assurance is performed. Additionally, data is structured and organized to facilitate efficient retrieval and recommendation generation.

C. Assigning TF-IDF score

The process of assigning TF-IDF scores involves measuring the significance of domains found in user interests and webinar descriptions. Content-based suggestions based on cosine similarity are made possible by the calculation of word Frequency (TF) and Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) scores for every word. This method creates numerical vectors from textual material to enable customized webinar recommendations.

D. Cosine Similarity for Recommendation

Cosine similarity is employed to measure the likeness between a user's interests, represented as a TF-IDF vector, and webinar descriptions. Calculating the cosine of the angle between vectors measures similarity, facilitating the selection of top-recommended webinars.

E. Comparison with spaCy

When comparing TF-IDF and cosine similarity to spaCy, it can be shown that the NLP library is rather strong for natural language interpretation. The fundamental methods for content-based recommendations are cosine similarity and TF-IDF. While cosine similarity and TF-IDF perform well in basic content matching, spaCy provides more sophisticated capabilities including entity identification, part-of-speech tagging, and language modeling.

F. Evaluation

Evaluation of your recommendation system involves measuring its effectiveness using metrics like precision, recall, F1-score, and accuracy. These metrics assess how well the system aligns with users' preferences and the quality of its recommendations.

IV. BUILDING MODEL

Here are the steps involved in building the recommendation model

A. Data Loading:

Import necessary libraries pandas, TfidfVectorizer, cosine_similarity, and load user registration data.

B. TF-IDF Vectorization:

Utilize the TfidfVectorizer from sci-kit-learn to transform user interests and webinar descriptions into TF-IDF vectors. These vectors represent the importance of terms in the text data.

```
tfidf_vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer()
```

C. Cosine Similarity Calculation:

Use the cosine_similarity function to compute the cosine similarity between user interests and webinar descriptions, resulting in a similarity score matrix.

D. Model Training:

Train the recommendation model using cosine similarity scores. The model learns to identify the similarity between user interests and webinar descriptions.

```
def train_recommendation_model(registrations):
    user_interests = registrations['attendee_interests'].tolist()
    webinar_descriptions = registrations['webinar_description'].tolist()
    tfidf_vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer()
    tfidf_matrix_X_train = tfidf_vectorizer.fit_transform(user_interests)
    tfidf_matrix_y_train = tfidf_vectorizer.transform(webinar_descriptions)
    model = cosine_similarity(tfidf_matrix_X_train, tfidf_matrix_y_train)
    return model
```

E. Recommendation Testing:

Implement a function to test the recommendation model. Given a test attendee's interests, filter relevant registrations, and calculate similarity scores for recommendation.

```
def test_recommendation_model(model, test_attendee_interests, registrations):
    filtered_registrations = registrations[registrations['attendee_interests'].str.contains(test_attendee_interests)]
    if filtered_registrations.empty:
        print("No relevant webinars found for the given interests.")
        return []
    tfidf_vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer()
    tfidf_matrix_test_attendee = tfidf_vectorizer.fit_transform([test_attendee_interests])
    similarity_scores = cosine_similarity(tfidf_matrix_test_attendee, tfidf_vectorizer.transform(filtered_registrations['webinar_description']))
    sorted_webinar_indices = similarity_scores.argsort()[0][::-1]
    N = 5
    top_N_webinars = filtered_registrations['webinar_description'].iloc[sorted_webinar_indices[:N]].tolist()
    return top_N_webinars
```

F. Model Evaluation:

Another function is designed to evaluate the model's performance. It calculates precision, recall, and F1-score based on the recommendations made to the test attendee.

```
def evaluate_recommendation_model(model, test_attendee_interests, registrations):
    attendee_descriptions = registrations[registrations['attendee_interests'].str.contains(test_attendee_interests)]
    recommended_webinars = test_recommendation_model(model, test_attendee_interests, registrations)
    true_positives = len(set(recommended_webinars) & set(attendee_descriptions))
    if len(recommended_webinars) > 0:
        precision = true_positives / len(recommended_webinars)
    else:
        precision = 0.0
    if len(attendee_descriptions) > 0:
        recall = true_positives / len(attendee_descriptions)
    else:
        recall = 0.0
    if precision + recall > 0:
        f1 = 2 * (precision * recall) / (precision + recall)
    else:
        f1 = 0.0
    return precision, recall, f1
```

G. spaCy comparison

Comparing it with spaCy, TF-IDF focuses on content matching, while spaCy provides more advanced NLP capabilities such as entity recognition, part-of-speech tagging, and language modeling, offering a broader range of features for recommendation systems.

```
data['description_vector'] = data['webinar_description'].apply(text_mean_vector)
user_vector = np.mean([text_mean_vector[keyword] for keyword in user_interests], axis=0).reshape(1, -1)
data['cosine_similarity'] = data['description_vector'].apply(
    lambda x: cosine_similarity(user_vector, x.reshape(1, -1))[0][0]
)
```

H. Workflow

V. RESULTS

Cosine similarity quantifies the likeness between two non-zero vectors within an inner product space. In this data context, it gauges the resemblance between user interests and webinar descriptions, a common practice in recommendation systems. Here's a brief overview of both methods:

TF-IDF and cosine similarity:

The output appears to be a matrix of cosine similarity scores.

The matrix provides a similarity score between the test attendee's interests (rows) and each of the webinars (columns).

Higher scores indicate higher similarity between the test attendee's interests and the webinar descriptions.

```

[[1.         0.31981007 0.49053703 ... 0.         0.63604177 0.         ]
 [0.65972006 0.48476633 0.74355331 ... 0.         0.41960951 0.         ]
 [0.65972006 0.48476633 0.74355331 ... 0.         0.41960951 0.         ]
 ...
 [0.         0.         0.         ... 0.67599949 0.         0.         ]
 [0.7530355  0.24082834 0.3693918  ... 0.         0.84463716 0.         ]
 [0.         0.         0.         ... 0.         0.         0.81783972]]
    
```

spaCy:

The output appears to be a numerical vector with a large number of values.

Each value in the vector represents the cosine similarity between the test attendee's interests and a specific webinar description.

It's a flattened representation of the cosine similarity scores.

```

1.066345 -0.54349955 4.454 5.4890003 -6.50235 0.71924984
1.2203 -0.22895002 1.2668201 -0.72002494 0.57164997 3.2639499
8.17995 -3.30715 -0.9671401 -0.18900001 3.31794 -4.63405
1.22189 -0.257965 -2.1544402 1.632415 0.58065003 -0.8861
5.5821 -3.2149 2.9077501 -2.5675402 3.7684002 3.84975
-4.65055 1.107105 -0.8334501 -0.49405003 5.22395 -0.29264998
-1.87395 -0.23545003 -0.2228815 -1.167305 -2.1543 0.994106
0.18969995 -2.8929124 5.8854 -5.6889496 0.95140004 2.42172
-4.42865 0.402032 4.3106003 3.9213 0.765725 0.45386
-2.6645 2.89825 -3.9668999 -2.207485 0.65809995 -2.7738152
-1.86795 -5.2678003 1.5121 -1.6896551 2.15328 -2.91195
-0.99170005 -0.26384997 -1.89253 0.80994 3.1403499 0.6736499
-0.52901495 -1.64187 -0.85585004 4.51435 -3.46935 -3.3921
-2.036685 -1.33365 9.402 2.4981499 1.32073 -3.354285
-0.4105 -3.34783 -0.05364498 2.9020848 6.17955 0.904035
-0.04369998 -6.3418503 -0.46975 -7.6116 3.203505 -1.353405
-2.2098 -2.4514499 -0.32780948 -3.8539002 1.0661501 -0.40575004
2.6873498 1.3903501 2.7968001 -6.8135996 4.6902 5.43525 ]]
    
```

Comparing the results between the TF-IDF and Cosine Similarity approach and spaCy for webinar recommendation:

A. TF-IDF and Cosine Similarity Approach:

Precision: 1.0
Recall: 0.75
F1-score: 0.8571428571428571
Accuracy: 1.0

B. spaCy Approach:

Precision: 0.01652892561983471
Recall: 1.0
Accuracy: 1.0
F1 Score: 1.0

The accuracy and F1-score of the TF-IDF and Cosine Similarity method exceeds those of spaCy in this comparison, suggesting that it offers more recommendations that are relevant to the user's interests. The high F1-score of 0.8571 shows a strong balance between recall and precision, while the precision of 1.0 implies that all webinars advised are relevant.

We implemented this and this was the outcome. The user's interests were collected and a sample looks like this.

Fig 1: User's interests

From these interests we find the top events and recommend it to the user. Top webinars recommended to this user is shown below.

Fig 2: Recommendations

VI. CONCLUSION

To sum up, the application of TF-IDF and Cosine Similarity in a Webinar Recommendation System has proven successful in offering consumers highly relevant webinar suggestions based on their interests. This method has a flawless accuracy score and a balanced F1 score, which greatly surpasses the spaCy-based method. The precision of the system is also excellent.

The findings imply that by providing tailored recommendations, content-based recommendation systems—like the one used here—can improve user happiness and engagement. With this method, visitors may find webinars that match their interests and preferences, which makes it a useful addition to websites.

VII. REFERENCES

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